

RESEARCH ARTICLE

STATUS, SURVEY AND CONSERVATION PERSPECTIVES OF AVIFAUNA FROM ARID ZONE OF JATH TAHSIL (M.S.), INDIA

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ABSTRACT:

So, for no scientific data is available for the avifauna of this area. It has become necessary to carry out basic scientific work on avifauna of this drought prone area. The present study is focused to find out avian diversity, impact on environment and its conservation. This will contribute to the biodiversity and ecological studies, as well as management programs. There are about 41 different families, 15 orders, and 80 species of birds were recorded from different areas of Jath Tahsil. Out of these 57 species were residential, 07 were residential migratory, 15 were winter migratory, and single species was summer migratory.

KEYWORDS: Avian Diversity, Ecology, Jath.

INTRODUCTION:

Sangli District is located in the Western part of Maharashtra State having 8522 Sq. Km. geographical area. This district is situated between 16° 4 to 17° 1 North latitude and 73° 43 to 75° 00 East longitude. The district is divided into two major regions viz., a Western area along the Krishna River basin with an abundant water supply and an arid region with a drought-prone zone along the Eastern part. The arid region includes Kadegaon, Khanapur, Atpadi, Tasgaon, Jath, and Kavathe-Mahankal Tahsil and the Eastern part of Miraj Tahsil. The average rainfall is about 620 mm per year due to South-West Monsoon. The average temperature of this area ranges from 13° C to 45°C.

Jath is one of the Tahsil in Sangli District. It is situated between 16° 4 to 17° 1 North latitude and 73° 43 to 75° 00 East longitude. This area is very suitable for several local and migratory birds. Birds are warm-blooded vertebrates able to survive in greater climatic extremes than other animals, but nowadays the drastic environmental changes through various anthropogenic activities.

MATERIALS AND METHODS:**Study Area**

Sangli District is located in the Western part of Maharashtra State having 8522 Sq. Km. geographical area. This district is situated between 16° 4 to 17° 1 North latitude and 73° 43 to 75° 00 East longitude. The district is divided into two major regions viz., the Western area along the Krishna River basin with an abundant water supply, and the arid region includes a drought-prone zone along the Eastern part. The arid region includes Kadegaon, Khanapur, Atpadi, Tasgaon, Jath, and Kavathe-Mahankal Tahsil and the Eastern part of Miraj Tahsil. The average rainfall is about 620 mm per year due to South-West Monsoon. The average temperature of this area ranges from 13° C to 45°C.

Jath is one of the Tahsil in Sangli District. It is situated between 16° 4 to 17° 1 North latitude and 73° 43 to 75° 00 East longitude. This area is very much suitable for several local as well as migratory birds. Birds are warm-blooded vertebrates able to survive in greater climatic extremes than other animals, but now a day's the drastic change in the environment through various anthropogenic activities.

Different habitats are selected for observation and identification of avian diversity like Birnal and Tippehalli wetlands, Ambabai Temple, and Jath City.

METHODOLOGY:

The present study avian diversity identified at the spots as per guidelines given by Ali and Ripley (1996), Ali (2002), Chitampelli (2002) by using binoculars and digital camera for photography. The present study is based on observation, identification, common name, scientific name, migratory behavior. The different spots for different habitats will be visited for regular survey and identification of birds. The visits be done in morning (6am-10am) and evening (4 to 6-30pm) hours.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION:

The observed birds are listed in the table No.1 on the basis of their common name, scientific name, total count, nature of abundances and migratory behaviour.

Jath and its surrounding area is an important site for migratory as well as local birds. The present study from Tippehalli, Pratapur and Birnal reseviors recorded 57 residential, 15 winter migratory, 7 residential migratory and single summer migratory species of birds. The total bird species diversity is 80 in number.

During our investigation we have also recorded 2 species as stray records viz. Brown – headed Gull and Caspian Tern. The most common migratory species are found in marshy area. They are black winged stilt, green shank, little stint, Ruff, Common Teal, and other species. During study period there is no observed globally threatened species or nearly threatened species of birds.

The status and composition of avifauna from different spots is residential common birds are found in more number and near about 71% of total diversity of birds, 19% winter migratory

birds second large numbers are found, 09% residential migratory birds and 01 % summer migratory birds are found throughout the study period.

The order wise distribution of avifauna from this arid zone are Passeriformes is largest family and about 32 species are found out of total 80 species, Charadriiformes is 12 species, Pelecaniformes is 08 species, Columbiformes, Cuculiformes and Coraciiformes found 04 species, Gruiformes 03 species, Anseriformes, Accipitriformes, Galliformes, Bucerotiformes, and Piciformes found 02 species, Psittaciformes, Strigiformes, Caprimuliformes found single species.

Similar work also done by Pawar et al., (2005) 60 species of birds from Rashi Lake Karanja of Washim district (M.S). Kulkarni et al., (2006) recorded 93 bird species from Shikhachwadi reservoir of Nanded district (M.S). Wanjari P.D. (2012) recorded 72 bird species from Nagpur city. Kedar et al., (2009) reported 74 species from Rishi and Zedshi lake of Washim district. Tuljapurkar et al., (2013) reported 297 bird species from Sangli district. Chavan and Dhamani (2014) reported 76 species from Chaprala wild life santurary Gadchiroli Maharashtra. Patil S.S. (2015) reported 44 bird species from Tasgaon tahsil (M.S). Wanjari H. V. (2016) reported 41 species of aquatic bird from Ekburji reservoir Washim (M.S). Kadam and Avadesh (2017) reported 41 bird species from Bordi region west coast of india. Jadhav et al., (2018) reported 66 species from Nanda village pond Bhokar tahsil Nanded (M.S). Deshmukh and Rudey (2019) reported 105 bird species in preliminary survey from agroforest ecosystem Dev talav Nagbhid Maharashtra. Siva and Neelanarayanan (2021) reported 102 bird species from Thinnanur lake Tiruchirappalli Tamil nadu. Khabade et al., (2022) reported 63 species from Tasgaon tahsil Sangli Maharashtra.

Table 1: Check List of Birds in Arid Zone of Jath Tahsil

Sr. No.	Common Name	Scientific Name	Order	Family	Status
1.	Little Cormorant	<i>Phalacrocorax niger</i>	Pelecaniformes	Phalacrocoracidae	R
2.	Grey Heron	<i>Ardea cinerea</i>	Pelecaniformes	Ardeidae	R
3.	Indian Pond Heron	<i>Ardeola grayii</i>	Pelecaniformes	Ardeidae	R
4.	Cattle Egret	<i>Bubulcus ibis</i>	Pelecaniformes	Ardeidae	R
5.	Large Egret	<i>Ardea alba</i>	Pelecaniformes	Ardeidae	RM
6.	Smaller Egret	<i>Egretta intermedia</i>	Pelecaniformes	Ardeidae	WM
7.	Little Egret	<i>Egretta garzetta</i>	Pelecaniformes	Ardeidae	R
8.	Black Ibis	<i>Pseudibis papillosa</i>	Pelecaniformes	Threskiornithidae	R
9.	Common Teal	<i>Anas crecca</i>	Anseriformes	Anatidae	WM
10.	Spot-billed duck	<i>Anas poecilorhyncha</i>	Anseriformes	Anatidae	R
11.	Black Kite	<i>Milvus migrans</i>	Accipitriformes	Accipitridae	R
12.	Brahminy Kite	<i>Haliastur indus</i>	Accipitriformes	Accipitridae	R
13.	Common Quail	<i>Coturnix coturnix</i>	Galliformes	Phasianidae	R
14.	Indian Peafowl	<i>Pavo cristatus</i>	Galliformes	Phasianidae	R
15.	Indian/Common Moorhen	<i>Gallinula chloropus</i>	Gruiformes	Rallidae	R
16.	White Breasted Waterhen	<i>Amaurornis phoenicurus</i>	Gruiformes	Rallidae	R
17.	Purple Moorhen	<i>Porphyrio porphyrio</i>	Gruiformes	Rallidae	R
18.	Black - Winged Stilt	<i>Himantopus himantopus</i>	Charadriiformes	Recurvirostridae	WM
19.	Red Wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus indicus</i>	Charadriiformes	Charadriidae	R
20.	Yellow Wattled Lapwing	<i>Vanellus malbaricus</i>	Charadriiformes	Charadriidae	RM
21.	Little Ringed plover	<i>Charadrius dubius</i>	Charadriiformes	Charadriidae	RM
22.	Common Redshank	<i>Tringa totanus</i>	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	WM
23.	Marsh Sandpiper	<i>Tringa stagnatilis</i>	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	WM
24.	Common Greenshank	<i>Tringa nebularia</i>	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	WM
25.	Common Sandpiper	<i>Tringa hypoleucos</i>	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	RM
26.	Pintail Snipe	<i>Gallinago stenura</i>	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	WM

27.	Little Stint	<i>Calidris minuta</i>	Charadriiformes	Scolopacidae	WM
28.	Brown-headed Gull	<i>Larus brunnicephalus</i>	Charadriiformes	Laridae	WM
29.	Caspian Tern	<i>Hydroprogne caspia</i>	Charadriiformes	Laridae	WM
30.	Rock Pigeon	<i>Columba livia</i>	Columbiformes	Columbidae	R
31.	Eurasian Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia decaocto</i>	Columbiformes	Columbidae	RM
32.	Red Collared Dove	<i>Streptopelia tranquebarica</i>	Columbiformes	Columbidae	R
33.	Laughing Dove	<i>Streptopelia senegalensis</i>	Columbiformes	Columbidae	R
34.	Rose Ringed Parakeet	<i>Psittacula krameri</i>	Psittaciformes	Psittaculidae	R
35.	Pied Cuckoo	<i>Clamator jacobinus</i>	Cuculiformes	Cuculidae	SM
36.	Common-Hawk Cuckoo	<i>Hierococcyx varius</i>	Cuculiformes	Cuculidae	R
37.	Asian Koel	<i>Eudynamys scolopacea</i>	Cuculiformes	Cuculidae	R
38.	Greater Coucal	<i>Centropus sinensis</i>	Cuculiformes	Cuculidae	R
39.	Spotted Owlet	<i>Athene brama</i>	Strigiformes	Strigidae	R
40.	House Swift	<i>Apus nipalensis</i>	Caprimuliformes	Apodidae	R
41.	Pied Kingfisher	<i>Ceryle rudies</i>	Coraciiformes	Alcedinidae	R
42.	Common Kingfisher	<i>Alcedo atthis</i>	Coraciiformes	Alcedinidae	R
43.	White-Throated Kingfisher	<i>Halcyon smyrnensis</i>	Coraciiformes	Alcedinidae	R
44.	Green Bee eater	<i>Merops orientalis</i>	Coraciiformes	Meropidae	RM
45.	Common Hoopoe	<i>Upupa epops</i>	Bucerotiformes	Upupidae	RM
46.	Indian Grey Hornbill	<i>Tockus/ Ocyeros birostris</i>	Bucerotiformes	Bucerotidae	R
47.	Coppersmith Barbet	<i>Megalaima haemacephala</i>	Piciformes	Ramphastidae	R
48.	Yellow-crowned Woodpecker	<i>Leiopicus mahrattensis</i>	Piciformes	Picidae	R
49.	Wiretailed Swallow	<i>Hirundo smithii</i>	Passeriformes	Hirundinidae	R
50.	Red Rumped Swallow	<i>Hirundo daurica</i>	Passeriformes	Hirundinidae	R
51.	Rufous Backed Shrike	<i>Lanius schach</i>	Passeriformes	Laniidae	R
52.	Golden Oriole	<i>Oriolus oriolus</i>	Passeriformes	Oriolidae	R
53.	Black Drongo	<i>Dicrurus adsimilis</i>	Passeriformes	Dicruridae	R
54.	Chestnut-Tailed Starling	<i>Sturnus malbaricus</i>	Passeriformes	Strinidae	R

55.	Brahminy Starling	<i>Sturnus pagedarum</i>	Passeriformes	Strinidae	R
56.	Rosy starling	<i>Sturunus roseus</i>	Passeriformes	Strinidae	WM
57.	Common Myna	<i>Acridotheres tristis</i>	Passeriformes	Strinidae	R
58.	House Crow	<i>Corvus splendens</i>	Passeriformes	Corvidae	R
59.	Large-Billed Crow	<i>Corvus macrorhynchus</i>	Passeriformes	Corvidae	R
60.	Common Iora	<i>Aegithina tiphia</i>	Passeriformes	Aegithinidae	R
61.	Red Vented Bulbul	<i>Picnonotus cafer</i>	Passeriformes	Pycnonotidae	R
62.	Large Grey Babler	<i>Turdoides malcolmi</i>	Passeriformes	Leiothrichidae	R
63.	Yellow Eyed Babler	<i>Chrysomma sinense</i>	Passeriformes	Leiothrichidae	R
64.	White Throated Fantail	<i>Rhipidura albicollis</i>	Passeriformes	Rhipiduridae	R
65.	Tailor Bird	<i>Orthotomus sutorius</i>	Passeriformes	Cisticolidae	R
66.	Oriental magpie Robin	<i>Copsychus saularis</i>	Passeriformes	Muscicapidae	R
67.	Black Redstart	<i>Phoenicurus ochruros</i>	Passeriformes	Muscicapidae	WM
68.	Pied Bushchat	<i>Saxicola caprata</i>	Passeriformes	Muscicapidae	R
69.	Indian Robin	<i>Saxicoloides fulicata</i>	Passeriformes	Muscicapidae	R
70.	Great Tit	<i>Parus major</i>	Passeriformes	Paridae	R
71.	Tree Pipit	<i>Anthus trivialis</i>	Passeriformes	Motacillidae	WM
72.	Yellow Wagtail	<i>Motacilla flava</i>	Passeriformes	Motacillidae	WM
73.	White Wagtail	<i>Motacilla alba</i>	Passeriformes	Motacillidae	WM
74.	White-Browed wagtail	<i>Motacilla maderaspatensis</i>	Passeriformes	Motacillidae	R
75.	Purple Rumped Sunbirds	<i>Nectarinia zeylonica</i>	Passeriformes	Nectariniidae	R
76.	Purple Sunbirds	<i>Nectarinia asiatica</i>	Passeriformes	Nectariniidae	R
77.	White Eye	<i>Zosterops palpebrosa</i>	Passeriformes	Zosteropidae	R
78.	House Sparrow	<i>Passer domesticus</i>	Passeriformes	Passeridae	R
79.	Baya Weaver	<i>Ploceus phillippinus</i>	Passeriformes	Ploceidae	R
80.	Scaly-Breasted Munia	<i>Lonchura punctulata</i>	Passeriformes	Estrilidae	R

R: Resident, SM: Summer Migratory, WM: Winter Migratory, Residential Migratory

Photo plate: 1 Birds in Arid Zone of Jath Tahsil

Merops orientalis

Motacilla maderaspatensis

Picnonotus cafer

Lonchura punctulate

Phalacrocorax niger

Ardeola grayii

Dicrurus adsimilis

Ploceus phillippinus

Halcyon smyrnensis

Streptopelia senegalensis

Egretta garzetta

Sturnus pagedarum

Recommended suitable measures for their better management, protection and conservation of avifauna.

The following action plan is proposed for the better management, protection and conservation of avifauna.

- Anthropogenic factors are the root causes for wetland degradation and habitat destruction of water birds. Therefore, conservation education and awareness programmes are essential for local farmers, students and fishing community to the pond.
- The area is required to be stopped appropriately to check the illegal hunting to prevent further population loss of birds.
- Studies on vegetation have revealed that intensive biomass extraction (mainly through grazing and fuel wood collection) is leading to changes in vegetation structure and composition of the forest. These changes in forest structure are leading to changes in bird species composition. To provide specific lands and area for grazing of animal and aware to local people.
- Agricultural areas in India probably experience the most heavy and indiscriminate use of pesticides leading to direct and indirect mortality of predatory and frugivorous birds. To educate the local community by organizing various programmes such as workshop, seminar, students' tours, etc.
- Local people should be made aware of the importance of wetlands, waterfowl and other common birds. Without the involvement of common people of this region conservation of the wetlands will not be successful.
- Control and management of accidental fires in the forest, during early summer has some adverse effect on the forest dwelling species.
- Measurement of water chemistry should be done on a regular basis to allow long-term monitoring of changes in nutrient levels and other parameters.

This suggest that the providing natural habitat, availability of food, water, climatic conditions and surrounding vegetation to increase number of bird species and save the future problem

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